

FROM THE EXPERIENCE OF TEACHING THERMOELECTRIC PHENOMENA IN A PHYSICS COURSE

¹Azimov U.I., ²Parmanov J.T.

¹Samarkand branch of Tashkent University of Information Technologies

²Samarkand State University of Architecture and Construction named after Mirzo Ulugbek

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Abstract. *Further improvement of the teaching of general physics courses for bachelors and special courses for masters is associated with an increase in the efficiency of studying each topic [1-3]. We judge the effectiveness of training by the depth and strength of students' knowledge, skills and abilities [4]. In this, a significant role is played by familiarizing students with the history of experiments, modern physical explanations of phenomena and their practical application.*

Keywords: *training, consideration, "Thermoelectric phenomena".*

Introduction.

Further improvement of the teaching of general physics courses for bachelors and special courses for masters is associated with an increase in the efficiency of studying each topic [1-3]. We judge the effectiveness of training by the depth and strength of students' knowledge, skills and abilities [4]. In this, a significant role is played by familiarizing students with the history of experiments, modern physical explanations of phenomena and their practical application.

This work is devoted to such a consideration, the main purpose of which is to increase the efficiency of studying the topic "Thermoelectric phenomena". A method for presenting thermoelectric phenomena is proposed, based on the laws of thermodynamics and quantum physics of solids [5-6], characterized by simplicity and accessibility for students to understand.

Let's consider a circuit consisting of two dissimilar materials M1 and M2, which can be two metals, two semiconductors, or a metal-semiconductor. The temperature of the junction is T₁, and the temperature of the free ends is T₂, with T₁ > T₂. In both materials, the kinetic energy of electrons at the hot junction is greater than at the cold ends, so electrons begin to diffuse to the free ends M1 and M2. This leads to the formation of uncompensated charges: the hot ends of the junction are charged positively, the cold ends - the free ends - negatively. The electric field acting between these charges prevents the diffusion of electrons, creating their counter flow. Equilibrium occurs when the flows are equal.

The potential difference between the free ends of the conductors is the thermo-emf. if the materials M1 and M2 are non-degenerate semiconductors, then at the hot junction, in addition to the entrainment of the kinetic energy of the particles, an increase in the concentration of charge carriers is observed. Therefore, an additional flow of particles moves from the hot junction to the cold ends, directed from an area with a higher concentration to an area with a lower concentration. Naturally, in this case the magnitude of the thermo-emf. there will be more.

Thermal emf value in a small temperature range is proportional to the temperature difference and the thermo-emf coefficient $E = \alpha_{1,2}(T_1 - T_2)$, or more precisely $dE = \alpha_{1,2}dT$.

Thermal emf coefficient $\alpha_{1,2}$ is the value of thermo-emf that occurs at a unit temperature difference; $\alpha_{1,2} = dE / dT$. Its values depend on the thermo-emf coefficients, branches of the chain

and is equal to their difference. Thermo-emf coefficient of various materials are determined in relation to lead, in which the thermo-emf. does not arise.

Thermo-emf coefficient can be positive or negative and depends on temperature. The values of some coefficients are given in Table 1 to obtain the maximum value of thermo-emf. that can be obtained by connecting two semiconductors of different types of electrical conductivity in a thermocouple. Investigating the temperature dependence of thermo-emf. semiconductor according to the sign of thermo-emf. is possible to determine the type of its electrical conductivity. In a semiconductor, there may be another mechanism for the occurrence of thermo-emf. effect of increasing electrons by phonons. At low temperatures, this is a component of thermo-emf. that may be hundreds of times larger than the one considered. In the presence of a temperature gradient in a solid, a flow of phonons appears, directed from the hot end to the cold, colliding with electrons and carrying them along with them - a negative charge is created at the cold end. The hot end will charge positively.

Table 1.

Material	Coefficient of thermo-emf $\mu\text{V}/\text{deg}$	Material	Coefficient of thermo-emf. $\mu\text{V}/\text{deg}$	Material	Coefficient of thermo-emf. $\mu\text{V}/\text{deg}$
Metals		Alloys		Semiconductors	
Sb	43	Chromel	+24	MOS	-770
W	3,6	Nichrome	-18	CuO	-696
Cu	3,2	Alumel	-17,3	CdO	-41
Pb	0	Konstantin	-38	FeS	+26
Pt	-4,4	Kopel	-38	NiO	+240
Bi	-6,6			Cu ₂ O	+100

The accumulation of charges continues until the potential difference balances the entrainment effect. This potential difference creates additional thermo-emf.

Theoretical studies of multiphonon resonant Raman scattering (MRRS) processes in a bulk semiconductor have shown that two types of processes contribute to the scattering cross section: scattering through intermediate states of free electron-hole pairs (EDPs) and through excitonic states.

Processes involving hot Wannier-Mott excitons have been studied in the case of a bulk semiconductor in a number of works (see references therein). Qualitatively, this scattering channel can be described as follows. When a quantum of exciting light is absorbed indirectly with simultaneous emission of an LO phonon, a hot exciton is generated. The exciton then undergoes a cascade of $N-2$ transitions through a real intermediate state with the emission of $N-2$ LO phonons and, finally, indirectly annihilates, emitting a secondary radiation quantum $\hbar\omega_s$ and the last phonon. When interacting with LO-phonons, the probability of emission of $N-1$ phonons by an electron does not depend on the dimensionless Froelich coupling constant $-\alpha_0$.

It follows that the contribution to the MFRRS cross section from processes involving hot Wannier-Mott excitons turns out to be proportional to α_0 .

This article considers two-phonon RSRS in a single quantum well in the case where the intermediate states are two-dimensional excitons. It is shown that in quantum well scattering there is only one indirect transition, which leads to a significant increase in the contribution of excitons to two-phonon RSRS compared to similar scattering in a bulk semiconductor. Let us consider the second phonon repetition, when the frequencies of the exciting light ω_l and the frequency of the scattered light ω_s are related by the condition $\omega_s = \omega_l - 2\omega_{LO}$ (where ω_{LO} is the frequency of bulk longitudinal optical phonons (LO - phonons)). In this case, for the scattering tensor we obtain

$$S_{\beta\gamma\beta'\gamma'} = S_{\beta\gamma\beta'\gamma'}^{(0)}(S_1 + S_2), \quad (1)$$

where
$$S_{\beta\gamma\beta'\gamma'}^{(0)} = (\pi\hbar^6\omega_s^2\omega_l^2)^{-1}(\hbar\omega_{LO})^4(2d/\pi a_0)^4 J_{\beta}J_{\gamma}J_{\beta'}^*J_{\gamma'}^*\delta(\omega_l - \omega_s - 2\omega_{LO}) \quad (2)$$

$J_{\gamma} = (e/m_0)P_{cv,\gamma}$. m_0 - free electron mass; $P_{cv,\gamma}$ - projection of the interband matrix element of the pulse, calculated on the Bloch modulating factors.

$a_0 = \varepsilon\hbar^2/\mu e^2$ - is the Bohr radius of the exciton, ε is the dielectric constant of the quantum well material, ε - is the electron charge, μ - is the reduced effective mass, d is the thickness of the well. Scalar functions S_1 and S_2 represent one- and two-fold sums over size quantization quantum numbers

$$S_1 = \alpha_0^2 \sum_n \int_0^\infty K dK I^2(K, n) [(1 + \alpha_v)^{-3/2} - (1 + \alpha_c)^{-3/2}]^4 \times \\ \times |G(n, n, K, \omega_l - \omega_{LO})|^2 |G(n, n, 0, \omega_l)|^2 |G(n, n, 0, \omega_s)|^2, \alpha_{v(c)} = (\alpha_0 m_{v(c)}/4 m_e)K, \quad (3)$$

$$S_2 = \alpha_0^2 \sum_{\substack{n, n' \\ n > n'}} \int_0^\infty K dK I^2(K, n, n') \{ |G(n, n', K, \omega_l - \omega_{LO})|^2 \chi(n, n', \omega_l) \times \\ \times \chi(n, n', \omega_s) + |G(n', n, K, \omega_l - \omega_{LO})|^2 \chi(n', n, \omega_l) \chi(n, n', \omega_s) \}, \quad (4)$$

Функции $\chi(n, n', \omega)$, $I(K, n)$, $I(K, n, n')$ имеют вид

$$\chi(n, n', \omega) = (1 + \alpha_v)^{-3} |G(n, n, 0, \omega)|^2 + (1 + \alpha_c)^{-3} |G(n', n', 0, \omega)|^2, \quad (5)$$

$$I(K, n) = \left(\frac{2}{x} + \frac{1}{b_n^2 + x^2} \right) \left\{ 1 - \frac{2b_n^4 [1 - \exp(-x)]}{x(b_n^2 + x^2)(2b_n^2 + 3x^2)} \right\}, b_n = 2\pi n; \quad (6)$$

$$I(K, n, n') = [\pi^2(n - n')^2 + x^2]^{-1} + [\pi^2(n + n')^2 + x^2]^{-1}, x = Kd. \quad (7)$$

In S_1 and S_2 , the Green's function $G(n, n, 0, \omega_l)$ corresponds to the direct production of an exciton, and $G(n, n, 0, \omega_s)$ - corresponds to its direct annihilation. These processes can only take place if $K = 0$.

$$|G(n, n, 0, \omega)|^2 = \left[(\omega - \omega'_g - n^2\omega_\mu)^2 + \gamma^2 \right]^{-1}, \omega_\mu = \omega_c + \omega_v - \omega'_g = \omega_g - \Delta\omega. \quad (8)$$

The Green's function $G(n, n', K, \omega_l - \omega_{LO})$ corresponds to the emission of a phonon by an exciton both for the case of scattering in the same zone ($n = n'$) and for the case of transition to another zone ($n \neq n'$). If the square of the modulus is

$$|G(n, n', K, \omega_l - \omega_{LO})|^2 = \left| \left(\omega_l - \omega_{LO} - \omega'_g - \omega_c n^2 - \omega_v n'^2 - \frac{\hbar K^2}{2m_e} \right)^2 + \gamma^2 \right|^{-1}. \quad (9)$$

Let us first consider the case in the same zone, described by the function S_1 . At frequencies $\omega_l < \omega'_g + n^2\omega_\mu$ all Green's functions are non-resonant (no real transitions) and $S_1 \sim \alpha_0^2$, which corresponds to background scattering. At the frequency $\omega_l^{(1)} = \omega'_g + n^2\omega_\mu$ real direct production of an exciton becomes possible, and at this frequency $|G(n, n, 0, \omega_l)| \sim \gamma^{-2}$

Since $\gamma \sim \alpha_0$, then $S_1 \sim \alpha_0^0$. At frequency $\omega_l^{(1)}$ there is a peak that is α_0^{-2} times higher than the background. In the frequency range $\omega'_g + n^2\omega_\mu < \omega_l < \omega'_g + n^2\omega_\mu + \omega_{LO}$ all Green's functions are non-resonant and $S_1 \sim \alpha_0^2$. Starting from the frequency $\omega_l^{(2)} \geq \omega'_g + n^2\omega_\mu + \omega_{LO}$ becomes resonant $G(n, n, K, \omega_l - \omega_{LO})$ (real phonon emission is possible). If the parameter is $\gamma/\omega_{LO} \ll 1$, then when integrating over the variable K , the contribution of the pole of the function $G(n, n, K, \omega_l - \omega_{LO})$ becomes predominant, therefore we can assume with sufficient accuracy that

$$|G(n, n, K, \omega_l - \omega_{LO})|^2 = \frac{2\pi}{\gamma} \delta\left(\omega_l - \omega_{LO} - \omega'_g - n^2\omega_\mu - \frac{\hbar K^2}{2m_e}\right). \quad (10)$$

Then in the pole $\omega_l^{(2)}$

$$S_1 = \frac{2\pi\alpha_0^2}{\gamma} \frac{m_e}{\hbar} \sum_n I^2(K_0, n) [(1 + \alpha_v)^{-3/2} - (1 + \alpha_c)^{-3/2}]^4 |G(n, n, K, \omega_l)|^2 |G(n, n, 0, \omega_s)|^2$$

$$K_0 = \sqrt{2m_e/\hbar} \sqrt{\omega_l - \omega_{LO} - \omega'_g - n^2\omega_\mu},$$

i.e. $S_1 \sim \alpha_0$. If $\omega_l = \omega_l^{(3)} = \omega'_g + n^2\omega_{LO} + 2\omega_{LO}$

(frequency corresponding to direct annihilation), then $|G(n, n, 0, \omega_l^{(3)})|^2 \sim \gamma^{-2}$ и $S_1 \sim \alpha_0^{-1}$.

Thus, the frequency dependence of $S_1(\omega_l)$ has two peaks: a weaker $S_1(\omega_l^{(1)}) \sim \alpha_0^0$, corresponding to real direct exciton production, and a strong peak $S_1(\omega_l^{(3)}) \sim \alpha_0^{-1}$, corresponding to real direct annihilation.

The frequency dependence S_2 differs from the frequency dependence S_1 in that at frequency $\omega_l^{(1)}$ $S_2 \sim \alpha_0^{-1}$, while $S_1 \sim \alpha_0^0$. The fact is that the function $|G(n, n', K, \omega_l - \omega_{LO})|^2$ can be approximated by a δ -function at frequencies $\omega_l^{(4)} \geq \omega'_g + \omega_c n^2 + \omega_v n'^2 \omega_{LO}$. The excitonic mechanism of two-phonon RSRS considered above leads to a sharp increase in the scattering cross section (scattering tensor $S_{\beta\gamma\beta'\gamma'} \sim \alpha_0^{-1}$ at the resonant frequencies of the exciting light) compared to EHPs as intermediate states ($S_{\beta\gamma\beta'\gamma'} \sim \alpha_0^2 \ln^2 \alpha_0$). Thus, scattering is entrained by a factor of $\alpha_0^{-3} / \ln^2 \alpha_0$. From this we can conclude that in a quasi-two-dimensional electronic system the excitonic mechanism of two-phonon RSRS is predominant. This conclusion seems justified specifically for two-phonon scattering, when the exciton appears only in the act of indirect production (or indirect annihilation) and single emission of the LO phonon. If the frequency of the exciting light is high enough so that the exciton energy is sufficient to emit many phonons, the question of the relationship between the contribution of the exciton mechanism and the EHP mechanism to scattering becomes more complicated.

This is due to the fact that when an LO phonon is emitted by a hot exciton, it can go into the EHP state and then phonons will be emitted by the electron and hole. Without examining the relative role of the two scattering mechanisms in this work, we only note that the dependence of the scattering tensor on the coupling constant α_0 in the case of MPRRS with a purely exciton mechanism remains the same as in the case of two-phonon RSRS, since the appearance of an additional coupling constant in the numerator during the transition from N to $N+1$ emitted phonons will be compensated by the appearance of the constant $\gamma \sim \alpha_0$ in the denominator, which comes from the process of real emission of a phonon by an exciton.

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